

Name	Geographic area	Type of entity	Outdoor / Indoor air	Pollutants measured
City Sense	European cities (Barcelona, Ostrava)	Research Institute	Both	NOx, Ozone
Air Casting	USA, Worldwide	NGO	Both	PM _{2.5} , CO, NO ₂
OPAL Air survey	United Kingdom	Research Institute	Outdoor air	NOx, NH ₃
Air Quality Egg	Worldwide	Collaborative Group	Both	NO ₂ , CO
Open Sense II	Worldwide	Research Institute	Outdoor air	O ₃ , NO ₂ , CO, CO ₂ , PM _{2.5} , UFP
Mobicit'Air	Grenoble city(France)	Public air quality network	Mostly outdoor air	PM _{2.5}
iSPEX	Netherlands	University	Both	Particles
Ambassad'Air	Rennes city(France)	Townhall	Mostly outdoor air	PM ₁₀ , PM _{2.5}
Citizen Sense	Pennsylvania (USA)	University, Public agencies	Both	BTEX, PM _{2.5}

Table 1